

AN EVALUATION OF ELT SITUATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

Ghulam Hussain

NCBA & E, Multan, Pakistan

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to evaluate ELT methods, techniques and to indicate classroom activities in the higher educations' institutions in Punjab particularly with reference to CLT. This study also focuses to point out hurdles and major training needs for improvement in ELT situation. Teachers of college and university are selected as participants for this study. Data is collected from one hundred and eighteen participants by using a questionnaire combination of open ended and close ended items. Data collected have been analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively in the form of percentage, tables and graphs. The findings show that with other teaching techniques and activities, CLT techniques and activities are also being used in our higher education institutions to some extent and similarly facts and figures about ELT success areas manifest that English language teaching in Punjab, Pakistan is moderately successful with respect to different aspects like reading speed, exam success, oral fluency etc. Teachers identified that conversation with native speaker is not as successful as needed. Teachers face many difficulties but these are manageable with respect to CLT. Mostly teachers suggested teacher training programme, use of new technologies, support from administration, small class size and training with native teachers to improve overall ELT situation.

Keywords: ELT, higher education, Punjab, Pakistan

1. Introduction

In practical life, this is commonly understood that English language provides a lot of opportunities for the financial success and also regarded as a marker of social importance. But unfortunately, the way in which English language is taught in our educational institutions do not enable students to use it very effectively in daily life

particularly in communication. In Pakistan, our classrooms are the major source of learning English, where English is taught by way of memorizing of English spelling, practice of grammar rules, translation of a piece of literature in mother-tongue (L1) and definition of grammatical structure and memorizing of text, which makes English boring subject. In our classrooms, English is taught by using some old methods and there is need to renovate it. There is need to teach English with examples from real life as used in the concept of "Applied English" (Khan, T. 2016). Due to conventional methods of teaching, an anxiety develops in the students and they lose their interest in this subject. Normally English is taught as an abstract system dealing with de-contextualized meaning but in communication, we need to understand meaning in particular context. Even abstract system reveals that, there are being taught only basic aspects known as semantics, morphology, phonology and syntax. When we check, and measure these five aspects meaningfully, can the teaching of grammar be justified?

Government and private employers, parents and students in Pakistan demand English. The same thing is verified by many surveys (attitude) conducted by Rehman (2002) and Mansoor, S. (1993). This same thing is confirmed by British Council of Pakistan and suggested that, for basic school level education, only mother tongue should be used and at higher level, English is more appropriate (Coleman, 2010). Punjab Education and English Language Initiative Report (2013) describes that knowledge of English language of public and private school teachers is very poor. This reports describes that student's parents admired instruction in English at school level contrary to fact that mother-tongue is more suitable for basic education. Rehman, T. (1996) pointed out that English is symbol of higher social status and also most attractive for employment.

In the 80's, there came a change, with teaching of English literature started teaching of linguistics, English language and English language teaching (ELT). This all was possible with efforts of aid given agencies of America and British council. In this regard, University Grants commission also arranged special courses and trained lecturers in ELT.

During the 1980's, the prejudice against language teaching of university teachers changed and in this regard University Grants Commission held a language conference in 1983. In this conference, most people favoured English Language Teaching (ELT). Allama Iqbal Open University in 1987 started M.A TESOL in distance education. Similarly, Azad Jammu and Kashmir University in the same year started two years programme in linguistics and M.A (ELT). Following the same tradition, University of Punjab and University of Karachi introduced M.A Linguistics in 1988.

Choudhry (1987) conducted a survey which shows that college and university teachers are 100% aware about the importance of English language in Pakistan at higher

level education. Rehman (1996) proposed that there is a need to teach functional English for daily life use at all levels of education including primary level education. But the most important is that no one has discussed what type of model of English would be suitable for our environment?

But in advanced countries, English language is being taught by using new kinds of teaching approaches like communicative type but Pakistan is developing country and our education is not advance to compete international standards. In some higher education institutions in Punjab, Pakistan, English language is being taught by using Communicative approach but not in all institutions. To evaluate current English Language Teaching situation in Punjab in term of Communicative language teaching, this study was carried out. On the above facts, the following research questions are framed;

1. Which types of techniques are used by the teachers in the classroom for ELT?
2. Which type of classroom activities are mostly used during ELT?
3. What are practices and opinion of teachers about ELT?
4. What are major difficulties faced by the teachers in ELT?
5. What are teachers' views about the effectiveness of ELT?
6. What are major training needs for teachers in Pakistan for better ELT?

This study aims:

1. To evaluate ELT techniques used by the teachers.
2. To indicate classroom activities in the higher educations' institutions in Punjab.
3. To find out the teaching practices and opinion of teachers about ELT.
4. To point out ELT hurdles faced by the teachers particularly with reference to CLT.
5. To find out the effectiveness ELT in Punjab, Pakistan.
6. To know major training needs to improve overall ELT situation particularly regarding CLT.

2. Review of the Literature

Kelley (1969) and Howatt (1984) have revealed that many current problems and issues in language teaching are not new to us and they have been raised throughout the history of language teaching. It is estimated that multilingual people in this world are nearly 60 percent. This bilingualism or multilingualism is not due to any policy but due to some natural settings and human needs. Now English is regarded as large scale studied foreign language and actually, five hundred years ago this English language was Latin.

The importance of this language can be estimated that it was language of education and trade. In the western world religious and all government, affairs were also dealt in this language. In sixteen century, a political change came in Europe and due to this change English, French and Italian got fame. But this political change proved harmful for Latin because its use as a spoken and written language gradually disappeared.

A new function of Latin Language started when its status changed from a living language to a less considered language in the school curriculum. Great works of Virgil, Cicero and Ovid were also written in Latin language. Latin served as an ideal and model for foreign language study from seventeen to nineteen century. Foreign language grammar and rhetoric were explained on the basis of Latin language model.

Kelley (1969) and Howatt (1984) discovered that from sixteen to nineteen century in grammar school in England children were taught Latin grammar which was considered as a base for grammar rules. These grammar schools children were also kept busy some kind of other activities like translation, writing practice of sample sentences, sometimes by using parallel bilingual dialogues and texts.

After acquiring the basic grammar of Latin then students were taught advance grammar and rhetoric. This learning of Latin grammar was dreadful dream for school children and in case of any failure, they were punished. For the improvement of Latin language learning and curriculum some reforms were proposed by Roger Ascham and Montaigne in sixteen century and Comenius in seventeenth century. Latin language decline changed educationist outlook towards the teaching of Latin language. Teaching of Latin's grammar stopped and its use for the development of intellectual skill remained only.

In 18th century, some modern languages became a part of school curriculum in Europe and these modern languages were instructed on model of Latin language. Those books were consisting of abstract rules of grammar, list of vocabulary items and translation of some sentences. Students read the sentence and then translate it into mother tongue and development of speaking was not priority. Students explained the grammatical system of these sentences and this was boring practice and no link to real communication. The translation of some sentences proved much laborious for them. For example: *"The Philosopher pulled the lower jaw of the hen"* (Titone 1968:28)

In 19th century, foreign languages were taught in schools on the basis of an approach developed on the study of Latin and gradually this led to grammar translation method.

2.1 Communicative Language Teaching

During the 1960s in Britain, many changes came in the tradition of English language teaching and in this period, the traces on Communicative Language Teaching are found. At that time, the main approach to English language teaching as a foreign language in Britain was Situational Language Teaching. Basic grammar structure was taught in the form of purposeful situation based- activities in Situational Language Teaching. But at the same time in United States in 1960s, the linguistic theory of Audiolingualism was rejected by the linguists, therefore in Britain, applied linguists started to raise questions about Situational Language Teaching.

Noam Chomsky, a prominent American linguist, in his book “Syntactic Structure” (1957) charged criticism at the structural linguistic theory. Noam Chomsky had stated that present structural language theories are unable to describe the essential characteristics of language like uniqueness and creativity of sentences produced by individuals. But British applied linguists took another aspect of language that was not explained by language theories at that time called functional and communicative potential of language. British applied linguists focused on communicative proficiency in language teaching rather than grammatical structure. Henry Widdowson and Christopher Candlin who were prominent scholars advocated this view of language. They got aspiration from the work of British functional linguists like M.A.K Halliday and John Firth, American work in the field of sociolinguistic by William Labov, John Gumperz and Dell Hymen and also work in philosophy by John Searle and John Austin.

Educational realities changes in Europe and this proved a motivation for different foreign language teaching approaches. At that time, major European countries were very much interdependent upon each other that are why a need to teach adult market languages was felt. This problem was examined by the Council of Europe that was a regional organization for cultural and educational cooperation. Council of Europe’s main focus was on education. Council of Europe arranged an international conference which was about language teaching, sponsored in publishing of books about language teaching and also played an important role in establishment of the International Association of Applied Linguistics. Council of Europe’s main focus was on the development of alternative method of teaching.

According to Van Ek and Alexander (1980:6) in 1971, an effort was done by a group of experts in order to develop language courses based on a unit-credit system. A unit-credit system is that in which we divide language tasks into portions. This group of experts studied European language learner’s needs and in this regard, a British linguist Wilkins (1972) prepared a first document in which he suggested functional or

communicative definition of language which may prove a base for developing a syllabus which would be communicative in nature.

The main contribution of Wilkins was communicative meaning analysis that is needed a learner in order to understand and express language. Wilkins tried to discuss the systems of meanings that is hidden behind the communicative use of language instead of describing a language through the concepts of grammar and vocabulary. Wilkins discussed two type of meanings called notional categories and communicative function categories. For example time quantity; location, sequence etc. are notional categories and offers, requests, denial etc. show communicative function categories. Later Wilkins changed his 1972 document into a book called Notional Syllabuses which has an important impact on the communicative language teaching development. Wilkins' commutative analysis was incorporated into set of specifications by Council of Europe for the development of first level communicative language syllabus. These efforts had strong effects on the design of communicative language textbooks and programs in Europe.

Council of Europe's work, Wilkins, Candlin, Widdowson, Christopher Brumfit, Keith Johnson and other British applied linguists' writings on the functional or communicative approach to language teaching, use of these ideas by the textbook writers, recognition of these new principles by the language teaching specialists, acceptance of experts of curriculum and British government gave it fame at national and international level, finally took shape of Communicative Approach or Communicative Language Teaching. This is also called notional-functional and functional approach. Communicative Language Teaching approach expanded in the mid of 1970s. This approach has two aims which are as following:

- a) The purpose of language teaching must be the development of communicative competence.
- b) The development of procedures for the teaching of four basic skills.

Its scope and status make it different from other teaching methods and approaches due to its comprehensiveness. For Communicative Language Teaching there is no universally accepted authority, text and model. Some experts regard Communicative Language Teaching as mixing of functional and grammatical teaching. Littlewood (1981) says that Communicative Language Teaching includes systematic attention to structural as well as functional aspects of language. But others say that Communicative Language Teaching uses procedures in which language learners' work in the form of groups or pairs by using language resources in problem solving activities. This communicative approach is differently explained by its supporters and practitioners in different way depending upon its use. For example, Savignon (1983) describes CLT by view of Montaigne that he learnt Latin by using CLT rather than

traditional method of learning language in which it is learnt through analysis and translation. Montaigne says that he learnt Latin without any proper method, a book, and grammar rules and without any difficulty as it is learnt from schoolmaster. Hilgard and Bower (1966) say that CLT this view of language learning can be referred as the experience approach or learning by doing. This idea of direct communicative acts is commonly central to CLT interpretations rather than delayed communicative acts.

Dell Hymes and Michael Halliday pay great tribute to Malinowski and Firth in the primary development of Communicative Language Teaching. Communicative Language Teaching's another dimension is that it is credited as experience-based and learner centered approach to second language teaching and by itself it has roots outside the language teaching traditions. In the 1930's American national curriculum commission suggested experience curriculum in English. Communicative Language Teaching is that theory language teaching which begins with communicative model of language and its use and that seeks to translate this into a design for an instructional system, for materials, for teachers and learner roles and behaviors, and for classroom activities and techniques.

Ahmad, S. (2012) conducted a study *"Applying Communicative Approach in Teaching English as a Foreign Language: a Case Study of Pakistan"*. The findings of this study show that communicative language teaching approach is better than the conventional method of English teaching called GTM. The finding of the experimental study show that if appropriate situation is created, then learners' communicative ability can be increased. Learners' motivation for learning can be boosted by using CLT approach. Survey results of this study show that CLT approach is possible to implement in Pakistan and teachers showed their interest to use activities in the classroom which come under CLT. Further findings of this study show that teachers have good understanding to use CLT. The main hurdles in implementation are lack of teacher training; students hesitate to use English in the classroom, over crowded classes and non-availability of suitable material.

Khan, A. (2013) also conducted a study on *"Teachers' views on the appropriateness and feasibility of CLT in Pakistan"* and in this study researcher checked a common view that is claimed by a number of scholars that Communicative Language Teaching approaches are inappropriate when used prescriptively or in non-native contexts. The findings of this study show that a mixture of traditional teaching methods and soft/weak version of CLT can be very useful for teachers of English as a second language. Although items of questionnaire and questions of interview were kind of neutral with respect to soft/weak and hard/strong versions of Communicative Language Teaching but results of this study show that innovations recommended by teachers were more closely to soft/weak versions of CLT. The results show that teachers

were not in favour of hard/strong version called task based language teaching that is now encouraged by many researchers of second language acquisition and in non-western countries in national education policies. The discoveries of this study show that most experienced teachers in Pakistan find it useful in their classroom with little modification in key components of CLT. The teachers were agreeing to increase their professional knowledge in the field of CLT.

Yaqoob, H. et.al (2015) also conducted a study on *“Constraints Faced by Teachers in Conducting CLT Based Activities at Secondary School Certificate (SSC) Level in Rural Areas of Pakistan”*. The findings of this study show that in rural areas of Pakistan, the oral communicative activities are not performed in efficient way and on the data analysis basis, it was observed that hurdles can affect the learning up to 75%. This study also indicates that impact of mother tongue, poor listening skill and little communicative proficiency are major hurdles in discussion and speaking during communicative activities. Since learners were belonging to peasant culture, want to adopt their forefather’s profession, and do not consider English language beneficial for them, therefore they have low motivation and no interest in speaking English. Due to large class size, it is not easy for teachers to motivate learners for speaking of English. Finding shows that sufficient time is another problem for teachers to communicate with students and there is also barrier of appropriate environment which is hurdle in motivation to speak English. In this study teachers pointed out that in our current examination system there is no oral exam that is why students do not focus on oral proficiency but focus only on grammar to get good marks. Deficiency of audio-video material is another barrier in creating real speaking environment. Learners have no computer and internet facility due to financial problems.

3. Research Methodology

It was important to use a qualitative research approach for this study because of the dependence on individual perceptions of a particular language teaching situation. It is a unique approach to research that draws mostly on multiple sources and on people's views and opinions of specific experiences (Aleixo, 2003).

Survey research design was selected for this study because this study heavily depends on teachers' self-reported feelings, personal viewpoints, and experiences about the ELT particularly with reference to use of CLT in the higher education institutions' classrooms in Punjab, Pakistan.

3.1 Population of the Study

All English subject teachers of seven hundred and fifty-six (756) higher education institutions in Punjab are population of this study.

3.2 Sample Selection

In teaching learning process, the teachers hold a significant position and impart their knowledge through different teaching methods. That is why one hundred and eighteen teachers were selected as research participants: get required information that was easily reachable and voluntarily available.

3.3 Description of Sample Population

The present sample was included teachers of both gender from different colleges and universities. This sample was included full time regular, part time and retired teachers. In this group of population, teachers were taken because they have first-hand knowledge and impart knowledge through different methods of teaching.

Sr. No	College/University	Sector	City
1	NCBA&E	Private	Multan
2	Women University	Public	Multan
3	University of Education	Public	Multan
4	Govt. Emerson College	Public	Multan
5	NUML University	Public	Multan
6	Govt. College Technology	Public	Multan
7	Marking Centre BZU	Public	Multan
8	COMSATS University	Private	Vehari
9	BZU Campus	Public	Vehari
10	Punjab College	Private	Vehari
11	University of Education	Public	Vehari
12	Superior College	Private	Vehari
13	COMSATS University	Private	Sahiwal
14	University of Education Bank Road Campuses	Public	Lahore
15	University of Education Lower Mall Campuses	Public	Lahore
16	University of Education Township Campuses	Public	Lahore

3.4 Reason for Selecting Questionnaire as an Instrument

In this study questionnaire is as an instrument due to many reasons. First of all, other data collection tool like interview and observation etc. required a lot time as compare to questionnaire. Secondly, it is considered most effective tool to collect information from participants. Third reason is that in order to maintain objectivity, descriptive analysis is

considered guarantee and lastly it had advantage to combine the qualitative portion of the research within the questionnaire for quantitative research.

3.5 Contents and Construction of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire contents were actually selected and determined by Khaled Mahrud Rezaul Karim in the Department of Curriculum and Instruction in University of Victoria. I discussed these contents with my supervisor Prof. Dr. Naveed Ahmad and my supervisor gave me suggestion to modify the questions because respondents may not be directly aware with CLT approach. My supervisor also asked me to seek permission from author of the questionnaire Mr. Khaled Mahrud Rezaul Karim.

3.6 Process of Data Collection

Questionnaires were sent in distant cities like Sahiwal and Lahore and these questionnaire received back to me by via Pakistan Post and TCS, but most of the questionnaires dropped at different universities and colleges received to me directly or through my friend by hand. Twenty questionnaires were also sent to International Islamic University Islamabad but no questionnaire received back. Total one hundred and eighteen questionnaires are collected from different colleges and universities directly or indirectly. One hundred and eighteen questionnaires received back from one hundred and fifty questionnaires, in this way return rate was 87.2% and mortality rate was 12.8%.

To collect data from English subject teachers of seven hundred and fifty six (756) higher education institutions in Punjab was very time consuming, expensive and hard to reach. Therefore, data was collected from one hundred and eighteen teachers of sixteen (16) higher education institutions located in Multan, Vehari, Sahiwal and Lahore that were easily reachable and nearby.

4. Results

Data analysis consists of several steps. First of all, questionnaires are arranged to record the frequency of each response of each question of the questionnaire. Then after careful reading and re-reading all responses of all questions are counted. Then after the count of each item, percentage is calculated and graphs are formed by using MS Excel 2013.

First three questions of the questionnaire were consisted of information related to participants. In first question, space related to age, gender is provided, and second question is related teaching experience at college and university. In third question, there was information about types of courses or classes taught in past three years. These questions are being omitted due to small number of participants because main purpose

of these questions was to take participants of equal sex, same age and same teaching experience. Selection of participants on this criterion required large number of participants but hardly there was available data of one hundred and eighteen participants.

4.1 Use of CLT and other Techniques

Actually, question one was designed to check the practices of Communicative Language Teaching techniques in our higher education institutions in Punjab. In fourth question, five items were included to check use of CLT techniques in our institutions. Those five techniques were as under:

1. Having a debate or role play.
2. Group discussion on a controversial topic.
3. Practice speaking in pairs.
4. Story telling in front of class.
5. Describing a picture to a partner.

Since the purpose of mixing of these techniques with other teaching techniques was to inquire indirectly implementation of CLT. From results of this study, it is clear that a small number of teachers said that they “never used” or “rarely used” these techniques. But teachers who used these techniques “regularly”, “often” and “sometimes” are large in number. So finally, it can be said that Communicative Language Teaching related techniques are being applied in our higher education institutions. The comparison between CLT and other techniques is shown in figure 1 and table 1.

Table 1: Use of CLT and other Techniques

Techniques	Use it regularly	Often use it	Use it sometimes	Use it rarely	Never tried
CLT	16.85%	29.11%	32.4%	17.09%	5.7%
Others	17%	24.73%	31.64%	19.02%	7.66%

Figure 1: Use of CLT and other Techniques

4.2 Use of CLT and others Activities

In question five, “pair work”, “group discussion”, “simulation/role play” and “call on students to orally respond to any issue/topic” are kind of activities which can be grouped into communicative type. These activities are being used in our higher education institutions at some extent. So the use these kind of activities at college and university level represents CLT atmosphere in Punjab’s higher education institutions. In these four activities, the option “never tried” is attempted by a small number of teachers as compare to “regular use”, “often use”, “sometimes use” and “rarely use”. Hence, one cannot deny the use communicative type of activities in our higher education institutions in Punjab. The comparison between the CLT and others activities is shown in Figure 2 and Table 2.

Activities	Use it regularly	Often use it	Use it sometimes	Use it rarely	Never tried
CLT	20.48%	36.20%	27.84%	14.11%	2.83%
Others	20.78%	27.65%	26.34%	17.58%	7.31%

Table 2: Use of CLT and others Activities

Figure 2: Use of CLT and others Activities

4.3 Teaching Practices

From results, it can be concluded that in teaching main emphasis is on teaching grammar which represents conventional type teaching environment but teachers consider their teaching environment as learner centered. In their teaching, they emphasis on communication in second language and on the development of listening and speaking skill but fluency over accuracy in not preferred.

On one side, teachers claim that their teaching develops strategic and sociolinguistic competence but on other hand, they deny that their teaching develops discourse competence only. On one hand, teachers admit that under learner centered approach, it requires a lot of time to prepare class activities but on other hand, they deny this fact that this approach puts too much pressure on teachers. Hence, form these results it is clear that their vision about their teaching practices is not clear.

4.4 Average CLT/ELT Difficulties

This question was actually designed to suggest possible difficulties in teaching of English language in Punjab, Pakistan, particularly with reference to communicative language teaching. Once again, in this question, CLT was not directly mentioned and in this question, all mentioned difficulties were largely related to CLT approach. From above results, it can be concluded that mostly mentioned difficulties are manageable. CLT approach in our current educational environment is applicable with management of these little difficulties. The only problem called “large class size” is equally suggested by the all teachers as minor, manageable, serious and major difficulty. The relation is shown in table 3 and figure 3.

No Problem	Minor Problem	Manageable Problem	Serious Problem	Major Difficulty
11.82%	19.47%	30.13%	25.64%	12.89%

Table 3: Average CLT/ELT Difficulties

Figure 3: Average CLT/ELT Difficulties

4.4 English Language Teaching Success Areas

In eighth question, there was discussion about English language teaching success areas. Overall results are evident of this fact that English language teaching in Punjab, Pakistan is moderately successful with respect to different aspects like reading speed, exam success, oral fluency etc. Teachers identified that oral fluency is moderately successful but conversation with native speaker is not as successful as needed. So there is need to address this issue with modern communicative type teaching approach like CLT. This relationship is shown in table 4 and figure 4.

Table 4: Average ELT Success Areas

Currently not successful	Little successful	Moderately successful	Successful	Currently most successful
12.95%	27.98%	34.13%	19.78%	4.92%

Figure 4: Average ELT Success Areas

4.5 ELT Training Needs

From overall results for the development of English language teaching, it can be concluded that the training areas suggested in this questionnaire are very important and mostly teachers agree with this. Two training aspect called “grammatical explanation of English” and “preparing English language material” are suggested by all teachers “important”. This actually reflects our conventional teaching environment. One training suggestion given by the teachers “Training of language with native” seems more practical. From teachers suggestion it is visible that mostly teachers are in favour of teacher training programme, to adopt new technologies, support from administration and grip on subject, small class size and training with native teachers.

Table 5: Average ELT Training Needs

Not important	Minor important	Important	Very important	Extremely important
3.61%	7.05%	30.78%	34.35%	22.54%

Figure 5: Average ELT Training Needs

5. Conclusion

The results of the study related to the implementation of Communicative Language Teaching techniques in our higher education institutions in Punjab discussed in one of the questions, show that a small number of teachers said that they “never used” or “rarely used” these techniques. But teachers who used these commutative techniques “regularly”, “often” and “sometimes” are large in number. So finally, it can be said that Communicative Language Teaching related techniques are being implementing in our higher education institutions to some extent.

In question five, “pair work”, “group discussion”, “simulation/role play” and “call on students to orally respond to any issue/topic” are kind of activities which can be grouped into communicative type. These activities are being used in our higher education institutions to a small scale. So the use these kind of activities at college and university level represents CLT atmosphere in Punjab’s higher education institutions. Hence, one cannot deny the use of communicative type of activities in our higher education institutions in Punjab.

The results about ELT classroom practices show that main emphasis in teaching is on teaching grammar which represents conventional type teaching environment but teachers consider their teaching environment learner centered. In their teaching, they emphasis on communication in second language and on the development of listening and speaking skill but fluency over accuracy is not preferred. On one side, teachers

claim that their teaching develops strategic and sociolinguistic competence but on other hand, they deny that their teaching develops discourse competence only. On one hand, teachers admit that under learner centered approach, it requires a lot of time to prepare class activities but on other hand, they deny this fact that this approach puts too much pressure on teachers. Hence, from these results it is clear that their vision about their teaching practices is not clear.

The results related to difficulties in teaching of English language in Punjab, Pakistan, particularly with reference to communicative language teaching, are evident of this fact that mostly mentioned difficulties are manageable. CLT approach in our current educational environment is applicable with the management of these little difficulties. The only problem called "large class size" is equally suggested a main difficulty by all the teachers.

Similarly, facts and figures about ELT success areas manifest that English language teaching in Punjab, Pakistan is moderately successful with respect to different aspects like reading speed, exam success, oral fluency etc. Teachers identified that oral fluency is moderately successful but conversation with native speaker is not as successful as needed. So there is a need to address this issue with modern communicative type teaching approach like CLT.

In the same way, results about training needs for the development of English language teaching, report that suggested training areas are very important and mostly teachers agree with this. Similarly from teachers suggestion it is visible that mostly teachers are in favour of teacher training programme, use of new technologies and support from administration, small class size and training with native teachers.

From results of this study, it is clear that this study would helpful for teachers in getting suitable professional development in effective strategies for ELT. This would also beneficial in indication of ELT difficulties and possible training needs in terms of Communicative Language Teaching. Textbook writer can also get advantage to include such activities which develop four basic skills equally particularly speaking skill.

References

1. Ahmad, S, C. R. (2012). Applying Communicative Approach in Teaching English as a Foreign Language: A Case Study of Pakistan. *Porta Linguarum*, 187-203.
2. Aleixo, M. B. (2003). Teachers' perceptions of communicative language teaching use in Brazil. Unpublished MA thesis, West Virginia University, West Virginia, US. Accessed on-line on June 5, 2003, from http://kitkat.wvu.edu:8080/files/2947.1_Aleixo-Marinathesis.pdf

3. Austin, J. L. 1962. *How to Do Things with Words*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
4. Breen, M., and C. N. Candlin. 1980. The essentials of a communicative curriculum in language teaching. *Applied Linguistics* 1(2): 89–112.
5. Brumfit, C. J., and K. Johnson (eds.). 1979. *The Communicative Approach to Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
6. Brumfit, C. 1980. From defining to designing: Communicative specifications versus communicative methodology in foreign language teaching. In K.
7. Candlin, C. N., C. J. Bruton, and J. H. Leather. 1974. Doctor-patient communication skills. Mimeo, University of Lancaster.
8. Candlin, C. N. 1976. Communicative language teaching and the debt to pragmatics. In C. Rameh (ed.), *Georgetown University Roundtable 1976*. Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press.
9. Chomsky, N. 1957. *Syntactic Structures*. The Hague: Mouton.
10. Choudhry, S. (1987). *Tertiary Level English in Pakistan: Literature versus Language Controversy*. Islamabad: Unpublished Survey Submitted as a Paper to the University Grants Commission.
11. Coleman, H. (2010). *Teaching and Learning in Pakistan: The Role of Language in Education*. Islamabad: The British Council.
12. Doughty, C., and J. Williams (eds.). 1998. *Focus on Form in Classroom Second Language Acquisitions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
13. Firth, R. 1957. *Papers in Linguistics: 1934–1951*. London: Oxford University Press.
14. Gumperz, J. J., and D. Hymes (eds.). 1972. *Directions in Sociolinguistics: The Ethnography of Communication*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
15. Halliday, M. A. K., A. McIntosh, and P. Stevens. 1964. *The Linguistic Sciences and Language Teaching*. London: Longman.
16. Hilgard, E. R. 1975. *Theories of Learning*. 2nd ed. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.
17. Hilgard, E. R., and G. H. Bower. 1966. *Theories of Learning*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.
18. Howatt, A. P. R. 1984. *A History of English Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
19. Hymes, D. 1972. On communicative competence. In J. B. Pride and J. Holmes (eds.), *Sociolinguistics*. Harmondsworth: Penguin. 269–293.
20. Johnson, K. 1982. *Communicative Syllabus Design and Methodology*. Oxford: Pergamon.
21. Johnson, K. 1984. Skill psychology and communicative methodology. Paper presented at the RELC seminar, Singapore.

22. Johnson, K., and H. Johnson 1998. Communicative methodology. In K. Johnson and H. Johnson (eds.), *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Blackwell. 68–73.
23. Karim, K. M. (2004). *Teachers' perceptions, attitudes and expectations about Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) in post-secondary education in Bangladesh*. Victoria: University of Victoria, Canada.
24. Kelly, L. 1969. *25 Centuries of Language Teaching*. Rowley, Mass.: Newbury House.
25. Khan A., R. W. (2013). Teachers' views on the appropriateness and feasibility of CLT in Pakistan. *Asian EFL Journal*, 4-26.
26. Khan, T. (2016, August 25). *English Language Teaching in Pakistan*. Retrieved from Dawn.com <http://www.dawn.com/news/663605/english-language-teaching-in-pakistan>
27. Littlewood, W. 1981. *Communicative Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
28. Littlewood, W. 1984. *Foreign and Second Language Learning: Language Acquisition Research and Its Implications for the Classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
29. Mansoor, S. (1993). *Punjab, Urdu, English in Pakistan: A Sociolinguistics study*. Lahore: Vanguard.
30. *Punjab Education and English Language Initiative Report*. (2013, August 22). Retrieved from British council: https://www.britishcouncil.pk/sites/default/files/peeli_report_0.pdf
31. Rehman, T. (1996). *Language and Politics in Pakistan*. Karachi: Oxford University Press
32. Rehman, T. (2002). *Language Ideology and Power: Language- Learning among the Muslims of Pakistan and North India*. New York: Oxford University Press.
33. Savignon, S. 1972. Teaching for communicative competence: A research report. *Audiovisual Language Journal* 10(3): 153–162.
34. Savignon, S. 1983. *Communicative Competence: Theory and Classroom Practice*. Reading, Mass.: Addison-Wesley.
35. Savignon, S. 1991. Communicative language teaching: State of the art. *TESOL Quarterly* 25(2): 261–277.
36. Searle, J. R. 1969. *Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
37. Titone, R. 1968. *Teaching Foreign Languages: An Historical Sketch*. Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press.
38. Van Ek, J., and L. G. Alexander. 1980. *Threshold Level English*. Oxford: Pergamon.

39. Widdowson, H. G. 1972. The teaching of English as communication. *English Language Teaching* 27(1): 15–18.
40. Widdowson, H. G. 1978. *Teaching Language as Communication*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
41. Widdowson, H. G. 1979. The communicative approach and its applications. In H. G. Widdowson, *Explorations in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 251–264.
42. Wilkins, D. A. 1972. The linguistics and situational content of the common core in a unit/credit system. MS. Strasbourg: Council of Europe.
43. Wilkins, D. A. 1976. *Notional Syllabuses*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
44. Wilkins, D. A. 1979. Notional syllabuses and the concept of a minimum adequate grammar. In C. J. Brumfit and K. Johnson (eds.), *The Communicative Approach to Language Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
45. Yaqoob, H. M. A. (2015). Constraints Faced by Teachers in Conducting CLT Based Activities at Secondary School Certificate (SSC) Level in Rural Area of Pakistan. *Educational Research International Volume* 4(2), 109-118

7. The following are some difficulties, did you come across these difficulties or do you think they might be difficulties for you in English language teaching in Pakistan?

No problem	Minor problem	Manageable problem	Serious Problem	Major difficulty
1	2	3	4	5

- a) Teachers' lack of sufficient spoken English competence

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- b) Teachers' lack of target culture (English) knowledge

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- c) Teachers' little time to prepare communicative materials

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- d) Students' low-level English proficiency

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- e) Students resist communicative class activities

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- f) Not enough authentic teaching materials to use

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- g) Traditional grammar-based examinations

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- h) Large class size

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- i) Non-availability of natural teaching contexts

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- j) Lack of training

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- k) Lack of effective and efficient assessment instruments of communicative competence

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- l) Lack of support from administration

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- m) Some social issues

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- n) Unsuitability of Western educational assumption in Asia

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- o) Other _____

8. Please indicate your opinion about the following areas of English language teaching in Pakistan?

Currently not successful	Little successful	Moderately successful	Successful	Currently most successful
1	2	3	4	5

- a) Reading speed

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---
- b) Cultural understanding of English countries

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

c) Read English text book/news paper	1	2	3	4	5
d) Oral fluency	1	2	3	4	5
e) Exam success	1	2	3	4	5
f) Preparation of ELT teachers	1	2	3	4	5
g) Reading comprehension	1	2	3	4	5
h) Speak with native English speakers	1	2	3	4	5
i) Vocabulary knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
j) TOEFL preparation	1	2	3	4	5
k) Effective teaching material	1	2	3	4	5
l) Convenient and equipped classroom	1	2	3	4	5
m) Other _____					

9. What do you think would be the priority for teacher training in Pakistan for the development of English Language Teaching (ELT)?

Not important	Minor important	Important	Very important	Extremely important
1	2	3	4	5

Need for more training of teachers in:

a) fluency in English	1	2	3	4	5
b) practice reading and writing in English	1	2	3	4	5
c) Techniques which promote speaking skills	1	2	3	4	5
d) cultural knowledge of English countries	1	2	3	4	5
e) grammatical explanation of English	1	2	3	4	5
f) use of video in the classroom	1	2	3	4	5
g) knowledge of language acquisition	1	2	3	4	5
h) assessing students	1	2	3	4	5
i) preparing English language material	1	2	3	4	5
j) using the internet to teach English	1	2	3	4	5
k) Other areas of training needed _____					

10. Do you have any suggestions about the successful implementation and practice of English Language Teaching (ELT) method in Pakistan? Please comment.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of English Language Teaching shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).